

CIRCE 1st Project Quality Report

31/12/2022 - 30/06/2023

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Executive Summary

The CIRCE Project Quality Report summarizes the results of the project internal activity of monitoring the quality of project management. This first report refers to the first six months of the project, from 31/12/2022 to 30/06/2023.

Disclaimer

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Introduction

A questionnaire was distributed among all project partners to assess their degree of satisfaction towards the management staff and activities. For confidentiality purposes, it was possible to complete the questionnaire anonymously.

The questionnaire contained 7 questions. Specifically, four questions asked the partners to rate the project management on a 1 to 5 scale from the point of view of overall satisfaction, effective use of communication channels, conflict resolution abilities, and resource management. Two yes/no questions were aimed at evaluating the management's communication capacity and leadership.

A final question provided the opportunity to freely express additional comments, suggestions, or feedback regarding the project management activities.

The results of the questionnaire are presented below. The constructive comments received are reported in the final section alongside the relevant recovery measure that we suggest (when feasible).

Results

1. On a scale of 1 to 5, please rate your overall satisfaction with the project management activities:

14 risposte

2. How would you rate the effectiveness of communication channels established by the project management team? (e.g., emails, meetings, project shared space)

14 risposte

3. Is the project management team adequately defining and communicating project goals, objectives, and deadlines?

14 risposte

4. How would you rate the project management team's ability to handle and resolve issues and conflicts within the project?

14 risposte

5. Is the project management team demonstrating effective leadership so far?

14 risposte

6. How well is the project management team managing resources (e.g., budget, personnel, equipment)?

14 risposte

Additional comments, suggestions, or feedback regarding project management activities

A few additional comments and suggestions have been received. Here we report the constructive comments categorized as per request, and the recovery measure we suggest when feasible.

Comment: *The only issue I am having some trouble with is locating the plethora of documents available on Google drive but I suppose this is a necessary evil. Keep up the great work!*

Request: Provide clear indications wrt.document location

Recovery measure: Project Reference Manual

Comment: *Maybe the decisions that need to be made are taking a bit a too long.*

Request: Speed up the decisional process

Recovery measure: See Project Reference Manual, section 5.5, Rules for approval of documents-

Comment: *Ideally there would be some mechanism for new team members to join. It may be too much to ask for everybody's approval, but people just appearing or an announcement 'here's a new colleague' is a bit odd.*

Request: Devise a protocol for new members to join

Recovery measure: Project Reference Manual

Comment: *Another concern is administrative and bureaucratic work. Ideally, we could keep this all to a minimum.*

Request: Keep administrative and bureaucratic work to a minimum

Recovery measure: The request cannot be granted because CIRCE has no power to act on the legal and administrative regulations.

Comment: *Regarding communication activities, while these are very important, perhaps at some point a reflection on which are most effective and which are less effective (and therefore not worth the effort) are in order.*

Request: Evaluate effectiveness of communication

Recovery measure: Include evaluation about effectiveness of communication in the next quality control.